

Fabrication of electrochemical sensor based on Eu₂O₃/rGO nanostructure for endocrine disruptor estradiol sensing. Theoretical perspective on the sensing mechanism

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No.	Atom	N	N+1	N-1	f_j^+	f_j^-	f_j^0
1	O	2.1677	2.1497	2.1781	-0.5025	-0.5014	-0.5032
2	O	2.1680	2.1403	2.1849	-0.4429	-0.3183	-0.4678
3	C	0.8803	0.8592	0.9185	-0.2887	-0.2933	-0.2857
4	C	1.0384	1.0217	1.0524	-0.1670	-0.1707	-0.1641
5	C	-0.6454	-0.6037	-0.6901	-0.1491	-0.1565	-0.1425
6	C	-0.5946	-0.5727	-0.6148	-0.1422	-0.1580	-0.1450
7	C	-0.5946	-0.5737	-0.6063	0.1336	0.1342	0.1332
8	C	-0.7339	-0.7172	-0.7501	-0.1253	-0.1238	-0.1256
9	C	-0.7467	-0.7302	-0.7572	-0.1594	-0.1586	-0.1595
10	C	-0.5329	-0.5224	-0.5493	-0.1945	-0.1964	-0.1901
11	C	-0.5344	-0.5237	-0.5502	-0.2144	-0.2136	-0.2150
12	C	-0.5344	-0.5257	-0.5409	-0.1782	-0.1793	-0.1794
13	C	-0.5375	-0.5289	-0.5438	-0.2442	-0.2427	-0.2453
14	C	-0.2986	-0.2169	-0.3990	-0.0486	0.0639	-0.0417
15	C	0.1932	0.2908	0.1106	-0.1711	-0.1664	-0.1661
16	C	0.2650	0.3487	0.0251	-0.0927	-0.0586	-0.1575
17	C	-0.1272	-0.0880	-0.1467	-0.1079	-0.0471	-0.2786
18	C	0.0028	0.0525	-0.0297	-0.1099	-0.0216	-0.3020
19	C	-0.2349	-0.1749	-0.2552	-0.1485	-0.0349	-0.2989
20	C	0.0496	0.0516	0.0627	0.1548	0.2333	0.1453

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